

Supplemental Figures

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Figure S1. Representative 3D segmentations of the depot volume with and without non-depot injection spread. A) Representative 3D segmentations of the non-depot injection spread for 1mL infusions at 10mL/hr. with 27G and 22G needles. The 3D segmentations show non-depot spread of the injectate into nearby vasculature. B) Representative 3D segmentations of the depot for 1mL infusions at 10mL/hr. with 27G and 22G needles. The non-depot spread into nearby collapsed vasculature is removed to create the 3D segmentation of the depot.

Figure S2. Representative 3D segmentations including non-depot injection spread for infusions using a 10mL/hr. infusion rate. A-D) Representative 3D segmentations including non-depot injection spread for 0.5mL, 1mL, 1.5mL, 2mL, and 2.5mL infusion volumes for 6% ECE infused with a 27G needle (A), 12% ECE infused with a 27G needle (B), 6% ECE infused with a 22G needle (C), and 12% ECE infused with a 22G needle (D). All infusions were performed with a 10mL/hr. infusion rate.

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Figure S3. Representative 3D segmentations including non-depot injection spread for infusions performed manually. A) Representative 3D segmentations including non-depot injection spread for 0.5mL and 1mL infusion volumes for 12% ECE using both 22G and 27G needles and 10mL/hr. and manual infusion rates.

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